

Dissecting the Frog: Understanding ChatGPT's Sense of Humour

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Abstract. As the popularity surrounding large language models like OpenAI's GPT series grows, it is crucial to explore areas where they still underperform, particularly in understanding humour. While models such as ChatGPT have demonstrated state-of-the-art results on benchmark tests (Brown et al., 2020), studies like Borji (2023) highlight their consistent failures in explaining jokes. This research investigates why such failures occur by analysing ChatGPT's ability to interpret humour using the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). GTVH suggests that jokes arise from the interplay of two semantically overlapping but fundamentally opposed scripts. This study hypothesises that ChatGPT's architecture would be able to identify these opposed scripts. To test this, ChatGPT was asked to analyse 14 variants of two novel jokes, each crafted according to GTVH's seven differences. Each version was presented five times, and the responses were qualitatively analysed for patterns in success and failure. The findings showed that ChatGPT consistently failed to identify the relevant scripts and often misallocated importance, frequently overemphasising noun phrases or relying on familiar patterns from its training data. These errors mirror those seen in tasks requiring complex semantic reasoning, such as the Adversarial NLI dataset (Nie et al., 2020). There were further difficulties in spatial and physical reasoning, consistent with Borji (2023). Thus, the hypothesis was falsified. However, the study successfully identified specific shortcomings of ChatGPT, which may inform future work on the model.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; humour analysis; semantics

1 Introduction

In recent months surprise, fear and amazement have been expressed, both on social media and through various news outlets, regarding artificial intelligence's ability to replicate human-produced natural language. Results from Brown et al (2020), the paper which was released alongside OpenAI's GPT-3 language model, show state-of-the-art or near state-of-the-art results on a number of benchmark tests. Casual use of ChatGPT (OpenAI 2022), a language model based on GPT-3.5 and fine-tuned to produce human-like conversation, can seem to support these findings. However, digging deeper into answers given by the model can begin to reveal some cracks. An area of difficulty for ChatGPT is humour, particularly when it is asked to explain why something is funny. An example of this is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: *Example of ChatGPT explaining humour (Miller, 2023).*

It is a commonly held belief that humour is an inherently human behaviour, integral to who we are as a species and unlearnable for AI. Unfortunately, humour is indeed so integral to human communication that any form of AI which wishes to mimic human conversation must display at least a basic understanding of it. The goal of this paper is therefore to understand how and why ChatGPT misunderstands humour. This is done through testing the model's ability to identify two pieces of information important to understanding a joke. As explained in Section 1, according to the Semantic Script Theory of Humour (SSTH) (Raskin, 1985), the key to understanding any joke is to identify its two overlapping, opposed scripts. Following this theory, this paper tests ChatGPT's ability to identify scripts with the idea that, through analysis of its answers, we may learn more about the process it follows and therefore the mistakes it makes.

In total, ChatGPT is asked to identify scripts in 14 jokes, giving five answers for each. These jokes were designed to be maximally informative, following principles in the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). Answers are scored on the extent to which the relevant scripts are identified. From this data some clear trends appear. Most importantly it seems ChatGPT is incorrectly assigning importance to words in the joke, leading to the misidentification of scripts. This may explain why it struggles to explain jokes. Section 1 gives background information on SSTH and ChatGPT. Section 2 describes how the jokes used in testing were designed. Section 3 then explains the testing method employed. Sections 4 and 5 give the results of this test followed by a discussion of their significance. Finally, in Section 6 this method is evaluated, and proposals are made for future testing.

2 Background Information – ChatGPT, SSTH and ANLI

2.1 The Semantic Script Theory of Humour

The test given to ChatGPT in this paper is based on the idea that, in order to explain a joke, a language model, or a person, must simply identify the two scripts within it which share two set relationships. This in turn is based on the Semantic Script Theory of Humour (SSTH) (Raskin, 1985). In SSTH, humour arises in a text from the presence of two overlapping but opposed scripts. A script here refers to a package of semantic information directly evoked by a word (Raskin, 1985, p. 81). It is the current hypothesis a person holds for a concept, such as an object or an event, which contains prototypical lexical and encyclopaedic knowledge about said concept (Raskin, 1985, pp. 82-83; Attardo, 2020, pp. 30-31). For two scripts to overlap means that the text is compatible, at least partially, with both scripts (Raskin, 1985, p. 99). The two scripts being opposed means that the situations created by each script cannot co-occur, one presents a real situation and the other an unreal one. For example, in the joke:

‘A man went to a hardware store and asked for some nails.
 “How long do you want them?” asked the sales assistant.
 “Oh,” said the customer. “I was rather hoping to keep them.”’
 (Tibballs 2006, p. 326)

The two scripts are ‘physical length’ and ‘length of time’. Both are evoked by the text and yet both readings cannot be true at once. According to SSTH, the humour in all jokes arises from these two scripts. The relationships are unchanging and thus, to explain any joke we, or ChatGPT, must simply identify the two relevant scripts. This is what is tested in this paper.

2.1.1 ChatGPT: Training Data and Architecture

To understand and predict how ChatGPT may perform at script identification, it is necessary to know more about its underlying architecture. Throughout this paper, various models of Open AI’s GPT technology will be referenced. ChatGPT is the model tested, specifically the version which employs GPT-3.5. A version of ChatGPT which uses GPT-4 is now available, however this was not the case at the time of testing. GPT-3.5 uses the same training data and underlying architecture as GPT-3 but has the benefit of extra, more recent training data from up to September 2021 (OpenAI, 2023).

ChatGPT’s task is to generate human-like speech. To do this, when given a prompt, it predicts which word should follow the last, repeating this process to form an appropriate response. These predictions are informed by both the prompt and behaviour learned during training. GPT-3 uses training data taken from five corpuses, each containing text scraped from books and web pages online (Brown et al, 2020, pp. 8-9). The words in these corpuses are broken down into smaller clusters of letters and punctuation to ease memory use and processing costs. These are called bite-pair-encoded (BPE) tokens. The five corpuses contain 489 billion BPE tokens in total. On top of this pre-training data, ChatGPT received finetuning to better adapt it to conversation (OpenAI, 2022). This included reinforcement learning, where answers given by the model were ranked by human judges with higher ranking answers being rewarded. This data allows ChatGPT to build a model of how frequently tokens appear and should appear together. This information is encoded through embeddings. Embeddings are strings of numbers, assigned to tokens, which capture various pieces of information about them. They act as coordinates on a multidimensional graph on which embeddings considered to be related are drawn together. This captures semantic relatedness. When one embedding is evoked, this can spread to closely related embeddings, partially evoking them too (Pilehvar and Camacho-Collados, 2020, p. 5). This mirrors the views presented in Raskin (1985, p. 81) regarding scripts and their relationships. Scripts are viewed as nodes linked together on a semantic graph. The length of these links reflects the relatedness of the

scripts. This allows us to understand overlap and opposedness. The two scripts will have short links to some of the same scripts. However, they will also both be linked to scripts which cannot coincide. ChatGPT employing a similar system may therefore allow it to capture the same relationships.

Furthermore, ChatGPT may be helped by its use of transformer architecture. In older language models, input sentences were compressed into a single embedding, making it difficult to capture the totality of the information in the input (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 81-82). The use of a transformer mitigates this issue as ChatGPT is able to access individual embeddings assigned to every token in the prompt and answer up to that point (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 71-82). This allows the model to deal with all tokens in the same way as opposed to favouring those produced or seen more recently. Furthermore, the transformer employs an attention mechanism. This assigns importance to each previous token related to its usefulness in determining the current token (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 72-74). This should allow ChatGPT to identify scripts evoked partially by various words across a joke, while ignoring irrelevant scripts.

2.1.2 ANLI Dataset Scores

Although it does not seem that ChatGPT has been tested on script identification before, Brown et al (2020) does give the results GPT-3 achieved on many standard language model tests, including Adversarial Natural Language Inference (ANLI). ANLI (Nie et al, 2020) is a dataset which asks a language model to determine the relationship between two texts: entailment, contradiction or neutral. It is designed to be challenging, with GPT-3 failing to achieve convincingly above random chance, 33%, in all but one condition, in which it achieved 40.2% (Brown et al, 2020, p. 63). It seems though that ChatGPT does at least have some ability to understand complex semantic relationships, however it does generally struggle. This paper seeks to learn more about why this difficulty occurs.

3 Joke Design

To gain the greatest insight into ChatGPT's process when identifying scripts, it was important that the jokes used in testing were designed to be maximally informative. The first step towards this goal was to avoid using jokes which had appeared previously in ChatGPT's training data. Jokes were created from scratch in an attempt to prevent this being an issue. A further advantage of this creative approach was that it allowed jokes to be tailored to test specific aspects of ChatGPT's process. This tailoring was informed by a follow-up theory based upon SSTH, the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). GTVH builds upon SSTH, splitting jokes into six Knowledge Resources (KRs): Language (LA), Narrative Strategy (NS), Target (TA), Situation (SI), Logical Mechanism (LM), and Script Opposition (SO). These KRs reflect choices in the construction of a joke. The description of each KR is based upon those of Attardo and Raskin (1991, pp. 297-309). Note that, at times, a change in one KR necessitates a change in another, particularly LA. The jokes, their relevant scripts, and the choices of KRs are given and explained below.

Joke 1 Original (OR) - Politicians are like fortune tellers, pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear.

Script A – Knowledge, ability, honesty, making accurate predictions

Script B – Corruption

Joke 2 Original (OR) - How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb?

Three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.

Script A – Simple, everyday task

Script B – Stupidity, lack of real-world knowledge or practical skills

Table 1: *Language choices*

	OR	LA
KR Description	The choice of words and syntactic constructions which make up the joke.	
Joke 1 Choices	Plain, simple	More verbose, less common
Joke 1(LA)	Politicians behave in a manner akin to clairvoyants, give them your money and they will say precisely what you wish to hear.	
Joke 2 Choices	Seeks numerical answer	Seeks reason in answer
Joke 2(LA)	Why does it take three reality TV stars to change a lightbulb? They think they need one to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.	

1(OR) represents how such a joke may be told in day-to-day life. By contrast 1(LA) uses more verbose language less common in natural conversation. This may make the scripts harder to access as 1(LA) is less likely to resemble text seen in ChatGPT’s training data. In Joke 2, both variants use plain language but 2(LA) changes the nature of the riddle. Instead of asking for a numerical answer, it asks for a reason. This change of ordering should not affect ChatGPT’s performance, thanks to the transformer’s access to the embeddings of the entire joke.

Table 2: *Narrative strategy*

	OR	NS
KR Description	The genre of the joke, for example it may be presented as a story or expository text, a series of questions and answers or a personal ad.	
Joke 1 Choices	Expository text	Question-and-answer/Riddle
Joke 1(NS)	Why are politicians like fortune tellers? Pay them and they’ll say exactly what you want to hear.	
Joke 2 Choices	Question-and-answer/Riddle	Question-and-answer sequence
Joke 2(NS)	‘Do you think one reality TV star can change a lightbulb?’ ‘No.’ ‘Two?’ ‘No. It takes three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.’	

1(OR) takes the form of an expository text. Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 376) found this was the most common NS across three joke databases. The format of 1(NS) is less common and splits the data relevant to identifying the two scripts in a different way. This should not cause issues given that the transformer can still access all embeddings across the joke. 2(OR) is a riddle which uses the lightbulb trope seen in many jokes. This was chosen in part due to the LM used in many lightbulb jokes and in

part so that a common trope and NS may be compared to a rarer one. 2(NS) uses a question-and-answer format taken from Attardo and Raskin (1991, p. 300). Poor performance on this variant may indicate that ChatGPT is over reliant on a template for lightbulb jokes seen frequently in its training data.

Table 3: Target

	OR	TA
KR Description	Who or what the joke takes aim at.	
Choices Joke 1	Politicians	Florida Senators
Joke 1(TA)	Florida senators are like fortune tellers, pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear.	
Choices Joke 2	Reality TV stars	Idiots
Joke 2(TA)	How many idiots does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.	

Politicians are a common target for humour, in fact Raskin (1985, pp. 222-237) dedicates an entire chapter to political humour. 1(TA) uses a similar but more specific target to test whether target specificity makes Scripts A/B less accessible. It may be that as opposed to Script A/B being directly evoked by 'Florida senators', the joke evokes Florida senators which in turn evokes the script of politicians which evokes Scripts A/B. This second route, if followed, may give more chances for ChatGPT to be led astray. Reality TV stars were chosen as the target for 2(OR) to try and minimise the offensiveness of the joke while still maintaining an association between Script B and the target. The use of 'idiots' in 2(TA) is intended to evoke Script B more directly than 'reality TV stars' in 2(OR). If ChatGPT scores much higher on this variant than any other, then it may be that it has difficulty with the script of 'reality TV stars' or simply with fuzzier, less direct evocations in general.

Table 4: Situation

	OR	SI
KR Description	SI refers to the props and setting of the joke, the scene in which the joke occurs.	
Choices Joke 1	Fortune tellers, paying someone	Antiques, buying something, auctions
Joke 1(SI)	Politicians are like prized antiques, they can be auctioned off to the highest bidder.	
Choices Joke 2	Changing a lightbulb	Drawing a picture
Joke 2(SI)	How many reality TV stars does it take to draw a picture? Three. One to hold the pen and two to move the paper.	

Here 1(OR) makes a human-to-human analogy, comparing politicians to fortune tellers whereas 1(SI) makes a human-to-object analogy, comparing politicians to antiques. It may be that the lack of human connection makes Script A less accessible as human qualities are not as easily evoked by non-human items. In contrast to 2(OR), 2(SI) involves a situation, drawing a picture, which, while common in life,

likely appears in jokes much less frequently than changing a lightbulb. Lower scores on this variant in comparison to 2(OR) would suggest that ChatGPT is reliant on the situation of a joke appearing frequently in its training data to identify its relevant scripts.

Table 5: Logical mechanism

	OR	LM
KR Description	All jokes to some extent use some form of faulty logic which requires a certain suspension of disbelief. LM reflects the type of faulty logic employed by a joke.	
Choices Joke 1	False Analogy	Reasoning from false premises
Joke 1(LM)	A fortune teller goes to speak to his friend. 'I've got to be honest with you, I can't do this job anymore,' says the fortune teller, 'all that happens is people pay me money and I tell them exactly what they want to hear.' 'Well, that sucks,' replies the friend, 'but at least it sounds like you could have a great career as a politician!'	
Choices Joke 2	Figure-ground reversal	Faulty Reasoning
Joke 2(LM)	How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to hold the bulb and two to look for a tool box.	

Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 371) found false analogy to be the most common LM. It is an example of faulty logic; two entities are presented as alike in some way when in fact this is not really true (Attardo et al, 2002, p. 13). In comparison, reasoning from false premises uses correct logic (Attardo et al, 2002, p. 10). If we share the apparent assumption of the friend, that politicians just say what they are paid to say, then there is no faulty logic in the exchange, and it makes perfect sense. All variants of *Joke 2* bar *2(LM)* employ the figure-ground reversal LM. The normally static item, the person changing the bulb, and the item which normally moves, the bulb, switch roles (Attardo & Raskin, 1991, p. 303). Understanding how and why this represents faulty logic, that would nevertheless lead to completion of the task, requires both world knowledge about how a lightbulb is changed and physical/spatial reasoning. Borji (2023, pp. 3-4) demonstrates that ChatGPT often struggles with tasks that require physical/spatial reasoning. *2(LM)* only requires world knowledge about how the script of 'changing a lightbulb' is normally carried out to understand the faulty reasoning employed. Success on *2(LM)* but difficulty with the other variants may point to issues with ChatGPT's physical/spatial reasoning. Difficulties with all variants, bar *2(SI)*, may be due to a lack of world knowledge about how a lightbulb is changed.

Table 6: Script opposition

	OR	SO
KR Description	The exact nature of the opposed scripts in the joke. Oppositions fall under three categories: ab/normal, non/actual (which present a real and not real situation) and im/possible.	
Choices Joke 1	Non/Actual – ability or honesty/corruption	Ab/normal - smart or ability/dumb or lacking ability
Joke 1(SO)	Politicians are like fortune tellers, they claim to see the future but really know nothing at all.	

Choices Joke 2	Ab/normal – smart/dumb or practical skills/no practical skills	Ab/normal – simple, practical task/conflict or drama
Joke 2(SO)	How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to change the bulb and two to have a screaming match about who broke the old one.	

Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 371) found non/actual SOs to be the most common. $I(SO)$ by contrast uses an ab/normal SO. While stupidity is not necessarily a script commonly associated with politicians, it is an example of a direct negation SO (Attardo & Raskin, 1991, p. 108). It may be that ChatGPT finds this type of opposition easier to identify than the more nuanced and indirect honesty or ability/corruption SO. The smart/dumb opposition in $2(OR)$ is common across many jokes. By contrast, the simple task/conflict opposition is unlikely to appear as frequently in ChatGPT’s training data. However, the frequency of the smart/dumb opposition may lead to it being much more weakly associated with ‘reality TV stars’ when compared to the SO in $2(SO)$. Higher scores on $2(SO)$ may point to issues with common scripts not being evoked strongly enough by weakly associated words.

Given these choices and the discussion in previous sections, I propose two hypotheses regarding ChatGPT’s performance. First that $2(TA)$ will be the highest scoring variant. This joke uses a direct negation LM, uses plain language in the form of an expository text, contains a common joke situation and uses a target which should directly evoke *Script B*. Despite this I also propose that ChatGPT will score higher on *Joke 1* than *Joke 2* overall. This is due to *Joke 2* employing the figure-ground reversal LM and ChatGPT’s difficulties with physical/spatial reasoning.

4 Method

As previously stated, the aim of this paper was to gather qualitative data from which insights may be drawn into ChatGPT’s process when identifying scripts. Whether or not an answer correctly identifies the relevant scripts is to a certain extent subjective. Changes to this experiment which may produce more objective, but less quality-rich data are given in Section 6. There is however still value in quantitative data as it makes spotting trends in the answers easier. Answers given by ChatGPT were therefore judged against 4 criteria labelled A, B, E and O.

A and B were considered fulfilled if *Scripts A* and *B* respectively were correctly identified. These scripts are somewhat fuzzy and thus they were considered to be correctly identified if the answer referenced one of the concepts given in Tables 2 and 3. Some variants required different scripts and these are also given:

Table 7: *Alternative answers to Joke 1*

Joke 1	
<i>Script A</i>	<i>Script B</i>
Knowledge, honesty, doing a job honestly, making accurate predictions, ability	Corruption, being bought
$I(SI)$ – Being valuable, being venerated or respected	$I(SO)$ – Stupidity, lack of knowledge, inability to make accurate predictions.

Table 8: *Alternative answers to Joke 2*

Joke 2	
<i>Script A</i>	<i>Script B</i>
Simplicity, ease, practical skills, reality TV stars as normal people	Stupidity, lack of practical skills, lack of real world knowledge, uselessness
	2(SO) – Over dramaticism, behaving in an over-the-top manner, conflict, emotion

E was considered fulfilled if the answer contained no incorrect extraneous information. O reflects whether or not the nature of the script opposition was correctly identified. This was not originally intended as a measure and is not explicitly asked for in the prompt, however the majority of answers, 91%, referred to the nature of the script opposition in some way. An answer which did not reference this was still given a point but is marked as ‘ / ’ in Tables 9 and 10. Data is therefore presented with two different totals, one excluding the O scores and one including them.

Each joke was presented to ChatGPT in the following format:

‘According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humour, a joke is compatible fully or in part with two different scripts. These scripts are also opposed in some way. Please identify these two compatible, opposed scripts in the following joke:

[Joke]’

The prompt was intended to be concise but sufficiently informative. There were no answers where ChatGPT completely misunderstood the task and therefore it seems the prompt succeeded in this goal. Each variant was presented to ChatGPT and then the answer was regenerated to give five answers for each variant, 70 answers in total. When given the task, the option for ChatGPT to learn from the prompt was turned off to avoid later answers being affected by the results of earlier ones.

5 Results

Tables 9 and 10 contain the scores of every answer given by ChatGPT. An x represents that the answer fulfilled the criteria while a – represents that it did not.

Table 9: *Results of ChatGPT’s attempts at identifying the scripts*

Joke 1 Scores																																										
Categories	Original					Language					Narrative Strategy					Target					Situation					Logical Mechanism					Script Opposition					Total						
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5							
A	x	-	-	-	1	x	x	x	x	-	4	x	x	x	-	x	4	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	20	
B	x	-	-	-	1	x	x	x	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	x	-	x	2	x	x	x	-	x	4	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13		
E	x	-	-	-	1	-	-	x	-	-	1	-	x	x	-	-	2	x	-	x	-	-	2	x	x	x	x	-	4	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13	
O	x	-	-	-	1	-	-	/	x	x	2	-	x	x	-	-	2	x	-	x	-	x	3	x	/	/	x	-	2	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13	
Total	3	0	0	0	0	3	2	2	3	1	0	8	1	2	2	0	1	6	2	1	3	1	2	9	3	3	3	1	1	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	3	9
Total+O	4	0	0	0	0	4	2	2	3	2	1	10	1	3	3	0	1	8	3	1	4	1	3	12	4	3	3	2	1	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	0	0	4	12

Joke 2 Scores																																											
Categories	Original					Language					Narrative Strategy					Target					Situation					Logical Mechanism					Script Opposition					Total							
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5								
A	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	-	x	x	-	-	2	-	x	x	x	x	4	x	x	x	x	-	4	30
B	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	x	-	-	3	x	x	x	-	-	3	x	x	-	-	x	3	x	x	x	x	-	4	x	x	x	x	x	5	18		
E	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	x	-	-	3	x	x	x	-	-	3	-	-	x	-	-	1	-	-	x	-	-	4	9			
O	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	/	-	-	2	x	x	/	-	-	2	-	-	x	-	/	1	-	x	x	x	-	3	x	x	x	x	x	5	13		
Total	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	2	2	1	1	8	3	3	3	1	1	11	1	2	2	0	1	6	1	2	3	2	1	9	3	3	3	3	1	13		
Total+O	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	3	3	2	1	1	10	4	4	3	1	1	13	1	2	3	0	1	7	1	3	4	3	1	12	4	4	4	4	2	18		

Graph 1: Total scores of joke 1 and joke 2.

Joke 1 Vs Joke 2: Total Scores

Graph 1 presents the combined scores for *Joke 1* and *Joke 2*. ChatGPT performed better on *Joke 2* both including and excluding scores for **O**, thus falsifying the hypothesis that ChatGPT will perform better on *Joke 1* than *Joke 2*. This result is surprising given ChatGPT's previous struggles with physical/spatial reasoning.

Graph 2: Joke 1 and 2 by score category.

Joke 1 and Joke 2 by Score Category

Graph 2 shows ChatGPT's performance on *Joke 1* and *Joke 2* broken down by score category. Highest performance was achieved in identifying *Script A* in both jokes, scoring 57% (20/35) and 86% (30/35) respectively. In comparison, *Script B* was correctly identified in 37% (13/35) and 51% (18/35) of answers. The strong scores of *Joke 2* in identifying *Script A* are likely due to the popularity of lightbulb jokes and discussions of them in ChatGPT's training data.

Graph 3: Total scores of joke 1 and 2 without O.

Graph 4: Total scores of joke 1 and 2 with O.

Graphs 3 and 4 give the scores of *Joke 1* and *Joke 2*, broken down by KR. $2(TA)$ was not the highest scoring KR, as predicted in Section 2, therefore falsifying that hypothesis. Instead, ChatGPT performed best on $2(SO)$, $2(TA)$ was, however, the second highest scoring KR along with $1(SI)$. Finally, ChatGPT failed to score at all on $1(LM)$. While the complete lack of scoring is a surprise, $1(LM)$ was designed to employ a rarer, more conversational LM. It seems this was difficult for ChatGPT to parse.

6 Discussion

6.1 General Trends

As shown in Graph 2, ChatGPT had much greater success in identifying Script A than Script B. ChatGPT's much stronger performance in identifying Script A in Joke 2 compared to Joke 1 is largely the reason that the hypothesis regarding relative performance on Jokes 1 and 2 was falsified. A reason for this success with Script A may be how and where each script was evoked within the jokes. Script A

in both jokes is likely to be the first, or one of the first, scripts evoked by a single key NP in the joke. In Joke 1, it is likely evoked by ‘politicians’ and to a certain extent ‘fortune tellers’, whilst in Joke 2, Script A is probably evoked by ‘to change a lightbulb’. In contrast, Script B is evoked by the sum of many scripts. In Joke 1, the combination of ‘politicians’, ‘fortune tellers’, ‘exactly what you want to hear’ and ‘pay’ may be required to evoke Script B. ‘Pay’ is in many ways the key word, many answers failed to correctly identify Script B as they didn’t mention payment in any way, as shown in answers 1(LA4) and 1(TA4). This likely also explains ChatGPT’s success at identifying Script B in 1(SI), as shown in 1(SI1) and 1(SI3). This variant contains multiple words which may evoke money/being bought, ‘auctioned’, ‘bidder’, ‘antique’ and ‘prized’, which in turn links to the script of ‘corruption’. These successes and failures point to an issue with ChatGPT’s attention mechanism, as it does not give enough importance to ‘pay’ for identifying Script B in Joke 1.

Figure 2: *1(LA4) (OpenAI, 2022).*

Figure 3: *1(LA4) (OpenAI, 2022).*

Figure 4: *1(TA4)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 5: *1(S13)* (OpenAI, 2022).

This links to a trend in Joke 2. Script B, ‘stupidity’ or ‘lack of practical skills’, was often missed in favour of the script of ‘over dramaticism’ or ‘frivolity’. It seems that these are the scripts most strongly evoked by ‘reality TV stars’ for ChatGPT. Therefore, instead of reconsidering this association, given the rest of the prompt, ChatGPT’s answer is tailored to fit this script of ‘over dramaticism’. This leads to answers such as 2(LA1), where it is suggested that the ‘spinning’ referenced in the joke is done in order to attract attention to the reality TV stars as opposed to being due to their supposed stupidity. This suggests that ChatGPT is placing too much importance on connections learned in its training data and not appropriately considering information given in the prompt. This may also be caused in part by issues with the figure-ground reversal LM and physical/spatial reasoning, as discussed further in Section 5.6.

Figure 6: 2(LA1) (OpenAI, 2022).

Finally, many answers contain incorrect/contradictory extraneous information. 2(NS1) provides an example of this behaviour. Only answer 1(LA3) contains no extraneous information at all. Often, this information comes in the form of an incorrectly identified opposition between scripts. This trend of overly verbose answers is acknowledged by OpenAI (2022) in their blog post introducing ChatGPT. They suggest it occurs because human trainers show a preference for complex, verbose answers which supposedly demonstrate more in-depth knowledge. This leads to ChatGPT being rewarded for such answers and therefore preferring them in the future.

Figure 7: 2(NS1) (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 8: *1(LA3) (OpenAI, 2022).*

6.2 OR and LA

ChatGPT performed poorly in 1(OR), 2(OR) and 2(LA), while achieving average scores in 1(LA). The exception to this is 1(OR1) which is a near perfect answer. In 1(OR) there is too much focus on negative scripts associated with ‘politicians’. 1(OR2) provides an interesting example of this. This seems to stem from an assumption that the two NPs, ‘politicians’ and ‘fortune tellers’, are the root of Scripts A and B. ‘Fortune tellers’ as a script and its associations are given too much importance, again pointing to issues with the attention mechanism. ChatGPT performs much better on 1(LA). Scripts A and B are both identified more frequently. It is not clear why this occurred, but it seems in part to be caused by ‘clairvoyants’ evoking ‘predicting the future’ more strongly than ‘fortune tellers’. Furthermore, the phrase ‘give them your money’ is given more importance than ‘pay’ is given in 1(OR), leading to the monetary aspect of Script B being evoked.

In both 2(OR) and 2(LA), Script A is identified in every answer. This result is not surprising given that changing a lightbulb is a common joke setup which ChatGPT is likely to have seen in its training data alongside explanations of such jokes. ChatGPT however has no success in identifying Script B. ‘Reality TV stars’ most strongly evokes the script of ‘over dramaticism’ and the rest of the prompt is not enough to change that. The lack of change between 2(LA) and 2(OR) suggests that changing the nature of the answer, from giving a number to giving a reason, had no effect.

Figure 9: *1(OR) (OpenAI, 2022).*

Figure 10: *1(OR2)* (OpenAI, 2022).

6.3 NS

Script A is more accessible in variant 1(NS), than in 1(OR). The reason for this is again unclear. The question-and-answer split leads to the positive aspects of politicians being more strongly evoked. However, this does not aid in identifying Script B. It seems ‘pay’ being at the start of a separate sentence did not assign it greater importance as there was still a failure to recognise the payment aspect of Script B, see 1(NS5). The uncommon NS of 2(NS) did not present an issue for ChatGPT. In fact, the further breaking down of the answer appears to have made Script B easier to identify, perhaps because it emphasises that ‘one’ is the expected answer to the original question.

Figure 11: *1(NS5)* (OpenAI, 2022).

6.4 TA

In Section 2 it was suggested that the greater specificity of ‘Florida senators’ may make Script A harder to identify. This was not the case. ChatGPT had no issues with ‘Florida senators’ evoking the scripts of ‘political duties’ and ‘honesty’. It seems that ‘Florida Senators’ was not an isolated script which would have to evoke ‘politicians’ before any other script for the joke to make sense. In fact, the greater specificity appears to have made Script A easier to identify. Variant 2(TA) was predicted to be the highest scoring. Although ChatGPT did have success with this variant, this hypothesis was ultimately falsified due to issues identifying Script B and the nature of the resultant opposition. These issues are

shown in 2(TA4). One script was deemed to be related to ‘physical comedy’. This seems to stem from an issue with physical/spatial reasoning, the figure-ground reversal LM and a misunderstanding of how the act of ‘spinning’ fits into this.

Figure 12: 2(TA4) (OpenAI, 2022).

6.5 SI

ChatGPT identifies Script B more successfully in 1(SI) than in 1(OR) and gives less incorrect extraneous information. The human-to-object connection does not seem to have had an effect, contrary to the suggestion in Section 2. As described previously, this success may be to do with greater signposting of the monetary aspect of Script B throughout the joke. In 2(SI), ChatGPT has difficulties identifying Script A. Where in previous variants the model seemed to have some world knowledge about how the script of ‘changing a lightbulb’ is normally carried out, this is not the case for drawing a picture. This leads to answers such as 2(SI1) and follows the reasoning given in Section 2. The combination of this lack of world knowledge with difficulties in physical/spatial reasoning also causes issues in identifying Script B.

Figure 13: 2(SI1) (OpenAI, 2022).

6.6 LM

1(LM) was the only variant in which ChatGPT scored 0%. As opposed to being caused by the correct reasoning employed in the LM, as suggested in Section 2, the issue again seems to stem from a failure to appropriately assign importance. The key word for evoking both scripts is ‘politicians’ however this comes at the end of the joke after a long section mainly focused on ‘fortune tellers’. ‘Fortune tellers’ and related scripts are then given too much attention leading to answers such as 1(LM1). This result is particularly striking given that 1(LM) reflects a style of humour very common in natural conversation. 2(LM) is the only variant of Joke 2 which does not require physical/spatial reasoning. This may have led to ChatGPT having greater success identifying Script B as its identification was instead largely reliant on world knowledge of how the script of ‘changing a lightbulb’ is normally carried out. It may also be helped by ‘tool box’ strongly evoking the script of ‘practical skills’.

Figure 14: *1(LM1)* (OpenAI, 2022).

6.7 SO

ChatGPT performs well on 1(SO). 1(SO1) and 1(SO2) are good answers which each score 100%. It seems that the script of ‘dumbness’ is either strongly evoked by ‘politicians’ or the commonness of ‘dumbness’ as a script in jokes prevented lack of association from being an issue. It may also be that the phrase ‘know nothing at all’ strongly evokes ‘dumbness’. ChatGPT seemed to place a lot of importance in ‘what you want to hear’, the final phrase of other variants which led it to miss out on the monetary aspect of Script B. 1(SO3) and 1(SO4) do still highlight ChatGPT’s tendency at times to simply list the scripts most strongly evoked by NPs in the joke, a behaviour also seen in Joke 2. 2(SO) is the highest scoring variant. This is likely because Script B is aligned with the script ‘reality TV stars’, which most strongly evokes ‘over dramaticism’ for ChatGPT. This further highlights ChatGPT’s difficulties in going beyond its first assumptions when identifying scripts. If the script to be identified matches these assumptions, then ChatGPT is likely to succeed.

Figure 15: *I(SO1)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 16: *I(SO2)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 17: *I(SO3)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 18: *1(SO4) (OpenAI, 2022).*

In summary, the two hypotheses proposed in Section 2 were falsified. ChatGPT performed better on Joke 2 than Joke 1 and variant 2(SO) was the highest scoring not 2(TA). One trend became apparent, ChatGPT appears to have issues assigning importance appropriately to words in the prompt. This led in some cases to key nuances of scripts being missed, e.g., the money aspect of Joke 1 Script B, and in others to irrelevant scripts being given too much weight, such as the script of ‘over-dramaticism’ in Joke 2. ChatGPT also at times relied too much on patterns seen in its training data, ignoring key information given in the prompt.

7 Evaluation of Method and Future Tests

This paper’s main goal was to learn about ChatGPT’s ability to identify overlapping but opposed scripts in jokes. This followed from an overarching goal of gaining a better understanding of how and why ChatGPT fails to explain jokes. I believe the method used to gain this information was ultimately successful. From the elicited answers, some key issues became apparent, primarily that importance or attention was being improperly assigned to different words in the prompt. This may help to explain answers such as Figure 1, where ‘afraid’ is assumed to be more important than necessary to the understanding of the joke, leading to a nonsensical answer. As a whole, ChatGPT seemed to grasp what was being asked of it. I therefore suggest that the testing method had merit. However, it was not without issue. This links to a secondary goal of this paper, the proposal of a method to test script identification objectively across model and experiments. The format used in this paper admittedly involves subjective judgement by one individual and would therefore be inappropriate for this task. One change could be to employ more than one person to judge answers. However, a better method may be to reduce the options for answers to a true/false binary. Examples of this are given in Figures 19 and 20. This method would allow for greater standardisation and objectivity as models could be marked against a pre-determined answer sheet. A format similar to the one in the ANLI dataset (Nie et al, 2020) would be appropriate, using joke-script pairs which a language model had previously failed to correctly identify.

Figure 19: Example of current method (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 20: Example of true/false binary method (OpenAI, 2022).

8 Conclusion

This paper set out to gain a better understanding of why ChatGPT at times fails to explain jokes. SSTH (Raskin, 1985) proposes that, in jokes, humour arises from a text containing two overlapping, opposed scripts. This led to testing ChatGPT's ability to identify these scripts and then analysing the elicited answers in order to learn more about its process. ChatGPT was asked to identify scripts in fourteen joke variants, designed using GTVH (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). Two hypotheses were proposed and falsified. Firstly, ChatGPT did not perform better on variant 2(TA) than any other. Secondly, it scored higher on Joke 2 than Joke 1, contrary to the proposed hypothesis. Analysis of ChatGPT's answers revealed some key issues, largely with how attention or importance was assigned. In particular, too much importance was given to NPs in the jokes, often leading to other key words being ignored as thus scripts being misidentified. Similarly, too much weight was given to patterns found in ChatGPT's training data, leading to nuances in the prompts being missed. Issues with physical/spatial reasoning, highlighted in Borji (2023) were present and often answers contained incorrect or contradictory extraneous data, an issue noted by OpenAI (2022).

Finally, modifications to the method employed in this paper were suggested. Further research could seek to build on this method. The first step in this would be to create a database of joke-script pairs, possibly consisting of pairs which ChatGPT failed to identify. This would create a purposefully difficult benchmark test, similar to the ANLI dataset. Once created, this database could be used to test whether the method as a whole is useful for understanding how ChatGPT identifies scripts and therefore how it explains humour.

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10 Appendix One: ChatGPT Answers

This appendix includes every answer given by ChatGPT (OpenAI 2022).

The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. Politicians are like fortune tellers - this script implies that politicians are skilled at making predictions or promises about the future, similar to how a fortune teller predicts future events.
2. Pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear - this script implies that politicians will say or do anything to get paid or win votes, even if it means going against their own beliefs or values.

These two scripts are opposed because the first script suggests that politicians are trustworthy and capable, while the second script suggests that they are untrustworthy and willing to compromise their integrity for personal gain. The humor in the joke comes from the ironic contrast between these two opposing ideas.

Figure A2: Joke 1 OR Part 1/5.

< 2/2 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, the two scripts that are compatible, yet opposed in the given joke are:

1. The script of politicians being like fortune tellers who tell people what they want to hear for a fee.
2. The script of people seeking advice or guidance from those who have special knowledge or insight into the future, such as fortune tellers.

The joke works because it brings together these two scripts in a way that creates a humorous contradiction or surprise. The two scripts are compatible because both involve the idea of someone telling another person what they want to hear. However, they are opposed in that one script involves a respected authority figure (a fortune teller) and the other involves a much-maligned group (politicians). By combining the two scripts, the joke subverts our expectations and creates a humorous twist on a familiar idea.

Figure A3: Joke 1 OR Part 2/5.

< 3/3 > The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians: This script involves the common perception that politicians often make promises or say things to gain favor or popularity, regardless of their actual beliefs or intentions.
2. The script of fortune tellers: This script involves the common perception that fortune tellers make predictions or tell people what they want to hear in order to gain money or other benefits.

These two scripts are opposed in that politicians are seen as figures of authority and power, while fortune tellers are often viewed as charlatans or frauds. The joke plays on the idea that these two seemingly different figures actually have something in common: they both tell people what they want to hear in exchange for something (votes or money).

Figure A4: Joke 1 OR Part 3/5.

< 4/4 > The two scripts involved in this joke are:

1. Politicians are like fortune tellers: This script sets up the audience's expectations that politicians and fortune tellers share certain similarities. Both are seen as persuasive and convincing, even if they are not always truthful.
2. Pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear: This script sets up the expectation that people can be manipulated and controlled through financial incentives. It implies that politicians, like fortune tellers, will say whatever the audience wants to hear if they are paid to do so.

These two scripts are opposed because the first script suggests that politicians are like fortune tellers in a somewhat positive sense, whereas the second script implies that their willingness to say whatever people want to hear is not necessarily a positive trait. By combining these two scripts in a humorous way, the joke exposes the audience's perceptions of politicians as both persuasive and manipulative.

Figure A5: Joke 1 OR Part 4/5.

< 5/5 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, the two scripts involved in this joke are:

1. Politicians
2. Fortune tellers

These scripts are opposed in the sense that politicians are typically viewed as insincere, manipulative, and self-interested, whereas fortune tellers are seen as charlatans who make vague predictions in exchange for money.

The joke suggests that politicians, like fortune tellers, will tell you whatever you want to hear if you pay them, which highlights the similarities between the two professions and reinforces the negative stereotype of politicians.

Figure A6: *Joke 1 OR Part 5/5.*

 The two compatible, opposed scripts in the given joke are:

1. The script of politicians as clairvoyants who can predict and fulfill people's desires or wishes.
2. The script of politicians as dishonest or insincere individuals who make false promises to gain money or power.

These two scripts are compatible in the sense that both involve politicians saying things that people want to hear. However, they are opposed because the first script portrays politicians as having a special power, while the second script portrays them as deceitful individuals. The joke relies on this opposition to create a humorous effect.

Figure A7: *Joke 1 LA Part 1/10.*

< 2/2 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians as clairvoyants, who can predict and tell people what they want to hear.
2. The script of politicians as untrustworthy figures, who will say anything to get people's money.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that the first script implies that politicians have some sort of supernatural ability to please people, while the second script suggests that politicians are manipulative and dishonest. The humor in the joke arises from the contradiction between these two scripts, and the recognition that politicians may indeed behave in both of these ways at the same time.

Figure A8: *Joke 1 LA Part 2/10.*

< 3/3 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians as clairvoyants who can predict and fulfill the wishes of their constituents.
2. The script of politicians as dishonest individuals who say what people want to hear in order to gain their trust and financial support.

Figure A9: *Joke 1 LA Part 3/10.*

Figure A10: *Joke 1 LA Part 4/10.*

Figure A11: *Joke 1 LA Part 5/10.*

Figure A12: *Joke 1 LA Part 6/10.*

Figure A13: *Joke 1 LA Part 7/10.*

< 3/3 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, the two compatible, opposed scripts in the given joke are:

1. The script for politicians - which includes characteristics such as being persuasive, skilled in communication, and adept at convincing people to support them.
2. The script for fortune tellers - which includes characteristics such as making vague predictions or statements that are open to interpretation and that can be tailored to fit the desires of the listener.

These two scripts are opposed because politicians are generally expected to tell the truth and be accountable for their actions, while fortune tellers are often seen as charlatans who are peddling false hope or manipulating people's beliefs. In the joke, the two scripts are blended together to create a humorous and ironic comparison between the two professions.

Figure A14: *Joke 1 LA Part 8/10.*

< 4/4 > The two scripts that are compatible in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians - which includes the idea that politicians often say what people want to hear, rather than what they truly believe or what is in the best interest of the public.
2. The script of fortune tellers - which includes the idea that fortune tellers will tell people what they want to hear in order to keep them coming back for more readings.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that politicians are supposed to be honest and represent their constituents, while fortune tellers are widely considered to be fraudulent and their predictions are not taken seriously by most people. The joke plays on the idea that politicians are similar to fortune tellers in their willingness to tell people what they want to hear in order to gain their support or favor.

Figure A15: *Joke 1 LA Part 9/10.*

 The two scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians: This script includes the expectations that politicians are supposed to represent the interests of their constituents, be honest, and have integrity.
2. The script of fortune tellers: This script includes the expectation that fortune tellers will tell their clients what they want to hear, rather than the truth.

These two scripts are opposed to each other because politicians are expected to be truthful and act in the best interest of their constituents, while fortune tellers are expected to tell people what they want to hear, regardless of the truth. The joke uses this opposition between the two scripts to create a humorous incongruity by implying that politicians are similar to fortune tellers in that they also tell people what they want to hear, rather than the truth.

Figure A16: *Joke 1 LA Part 10/10.*

< 1/2 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, this joke involves two scripts that are compatible, yet opposed: the script of political representation and the script of fortune-telling.

The script of political representation involves elected officials who are expected to represent the interests of their constituents. However, the joke suggests that Florida senators are like fortune-tellers, who will say whatever the person paying them wants to hear, regardless of their actual beliefs or responsibilities.

The script of fortune-telling involves individuals who claim to have supernatural abilities to predict the future. The joke uses this script to draw a comparison between the unscrupulous behavior of fortune-tellers and the allegedly unscrupulous behavior of Florida senators who prioritize personal gain over representing their constituents.

Figure A17: *Joke 1 LA Part 1/3.*

< 2/2 > The two scripts involved in this joke are:

1. The script of a politician or elected representative: This script involves the idea that politicians are elected to represent the interests of their constituents and uphold the principles of democracy. They are expected to work for the betterment of their community and make decisions based on the needs of the people they serve.
2. The script of a fortune teller: This script involves the idea that a fortune teller tells people what they want to hear, often making vague and generalized statements to please their clients. The implication here is that the senators in Florida are like fortune tellers in that they will say whatever their constituents want to hear, rather than making decisions based on what is best for the community as a whole.

These two scripts are compatible in the sense that politicians often try to please their constituents and say what they want to hear in order to stay in power. However, they are opposed in the sense that the role of a politician is to serve the community and make decisions based on what is best for the public interest, while the role of a fortune teller is to entertain and provide comfort to their clients.

Figure A18: *Joke 1 LA Part 2/3.*

< 3/3 > The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke, according to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, are:

1. The script of "senators as politicians": This script includes the notion that senators are elected officials who are supposed to represent the interests of their constituents and make decisions based on what is best for the state or country. This script is opposed to the idea that senators are like fortune tellers who will say whatever they are paid to say.
2. The script of "fortune tellers as fraudulent": This script includes the notion that fortune tellers are often seen as scam artists who will say whatever their clients want to hear in order to take their money. This script is opposed to the idea that senators should be honest and trustworthy representatives of the people.

So, the humor in the joke comes from the unexpected and illogical comparison of Florida senators to fortune tellers, as it violates the expectations of both scripts and creates a surprise.

Figure A19: *Joke 1 LA Part 3/3.*

< 4 / 4 > In the given joke, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as:

1. "Politicians" script: This script refers to the perception of politicians as individuals who hold positions of power and influence in society, often associated with making decisions and enacting policies for the public good. It highlights their role in governance and public service.
2. "Prized antiques" script: This script refers to valuable and sought-after objects that collectors desire. Antiques are often considered rare and hold significant historical or artistic value. They are typically associated with auctions and fetching high prices from enthusiastic buyers.

The opposition between these two scripts lies in the humorous twist that suggests politicians, like prized antiques, can be "auctioned off to the highest bidder." This implies a negative aspect of politicians, suggesting that their actions and loyalties may be influenced or swayed by financial interests rather than serving the public's best interests. This contrast between the noble perception of politicians and the satirical idea of their susceptibility to bribery or corruption creates the comedic effect.

Figure A20: *Joke 1 SI Part 1/5.*

 In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Politicians as prized antiques: This script portrays politicians as valuable and sought-after individuals, similar to prized antiques. It implies that politicians have a certain worth or value that can be recognized and appreciated.
2. Politicians being auctioned off to the highest bidder: This script suggests a negative perception of politicians, highlighting the perception that they can be influenced or bought by the highest bidder. It alludes to corruption, where politicians may prioritize the interests of those who provide the most financial support or favors.

These two scripts are compatible as they both involve politicians, but they are opposed in their portrayal. The first script presents politicians in a positive light, emphasizing their value, while the second script takes a more cynical perspective, suggesting they can be influenced or controlled by money.

Figure A21: *Joke 1 SI Part 2/5.*

< 2 / 2 > In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Script 1: "Politicians as respected figures or valuable assets."
This script portrays politicians as important individuals who hold significant value, similar to prized antiques. It emphasizes their perceived worth and the notion that they are desirable or sought-after.
2. Script 2: "Politicians as susceptible to corruption or being influenced by money."
This script highlights the stereotype or perception that politicians can be swayed or influenced by financial incentives. It suggests that politicians can be "auctioned off" to the highest bidder, implying a negative aspect of their integrity and suggesting potential corruption or lack of ethical behavior.

These two scripts are compatible in the joke as they merge the idea of politicians being valuable (like prized antiques) with the notion that they can be bought or influenced by money (auctioned off to the highest bidder). The joke derives its humor from the unexpected and satirical combination of these two opposing perspectives.

Figure A22: *Joke 1 SI Part 3/5.*

< 3/3 > In the given joke, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Script 1: Politicians as respected figures or valuable assets.
This script presents politicians as individuals who hold significant value or importance, similar to prized antiques. It establishes a positive or respectable perception of politicians.
2. Script 2: Politicians involved in corruption or unethical practices.
This script portrays politicians as being susceptible to being bought or influenced by the highest bidder. It suggests that politicians can be corrupted, contrasting with the notion of them being respected figures.

The humor in this joke arises from the incongruity between the two scripts. It combines the positive perception of politicians as valuable assets with the negative implication that they can be easily swayed by money.

Figure A23: *Joke 1 SI Part 4/5.*

< 5/5 > In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Script 1: "Politicians" - This script presents politicians as individuals with power and influence, often associated with corruption or questionable moral conduct. It highlights the perception that politicians can be influenced or bought by the highest bidder, implying a lack of integrity.
2. Script 2: "Prized antiques" - This script portrays prized antiques as valuable and desirable items, typically associated with rarity, beauty, and a sense of history. Antiques are often perceived as objects of high worth and are subject to auctions, where people bid competitively to acquire them.

The compatibility between these two scripts lies in the notion that politicians, like prized antiques, can be "auctioned off" or influenced by the highest bidder. The humor emerges from the unexpected and satirical comparison between the two domains, highlighting the perceived lack of integrity in politicians by likening them to objects of monetary value.

Figure A24: *Joke 1 SI Part 5/5.*

 The two scripts in this joke that are compatible and opposed are:

1. The script of a fortune teller who is expected to tell the truth about the future and provide insights to the person seeking their services.
2. The script of a politician who is expected to tell people what they want to hear, even if it may not be entirely true or accurate.

The humor in the joke comes from the contrast between these two roles and the irony that the fortune teller is unable to continue because he is telling people exactly what they want to hear, which is precisely what politicians are expected to do.

Figure A25: *Joke 1 LM Part 1/4.*

Figure A26: *Joke 1 LM Part 2/4.*

Figure A27: *Joke 1 LM Part 3/4.*

Figure A28: *Joke 1 LM Part 4/4.*

 The two scripts involved in this joke are:

1. The script of politicians claiming to have knowledge and expertise about the future.
2. The script of fortune tellers who claim to have knowledge of the future but are not taken seriously by the majority of people.

These two scripts are opposed because politicians are typically seen as credible sources of information and are expected to be knowledgeable about the future, whereas fortune tellers are viewed as charlatans who make baseless claims. The joke works by playing with the audience's expectations of what a politician should be, and then revealing the unexpected comparison to a fortune teller, which is a surprising and humorous twist.

Figure A29: *Joke 1 SO Part 1/5.*

< 4/4 > The two scripts that are compatible, yet opposed in the given joke are:

1. Script of Politicians: This script refers to the set of characteristics, behaviors, and expectations associated with politicians, such as making promises, being persuasive, and seeking power.
2. Script of Fortune Tellers: This script refers to the set of characteristics, behaviors, and expectations associated with fortune tellers, such as predicting the future, using vague language, and claiming special knowledge or powers.

The joke compares and contrasts these two scripts by suggesting that politicians, like fortune tellers, claim to have knowledge of the future, but in reality, they know nothing at all. The humor in the joke arises from the unexpected comparison between the two scripts and the ironic twist that both are equally unreliable.

Figure A30: *Joke 1 SO Part 2/5.*

< 3/3 > The two scripts at play in this joke are the script of "politicians" and the script of "fortune tellers."

The script of politicians implies that they have power and authority, while the script of fortune tellers implies that they are fraudulent and make false claims about the future.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that politicians are generally regarded as legitimate figures in society, while fortune tellers are often seen as frauds or charlatans.

However, the joke draws a parallel between the two scripts by suggesting that politicians are also making false claims about the future, much like fortune tellers. This creates a humorous incongruity that relies on the listener's recognition of the two opposing scripts.

Figure A31: *Joke 1 SO Part 3/5.*

< 5/5 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in the given joke are:

1. The script for politicians: This script includes the commonly held perception that politicians are supposed to have a deep understanding of the issues and challenges facing their constituents. They are expected to be knowledgeable and capable of predicting the outcomes of their policies.
2. The script for fortune tellers: This script includes the notion that fortune tellers claim to have supernatural powers that enable them to see into the future. However, in reality, they have no real insight into what will happen.

The two scripts are compatible in the sense that both politicians and fortune tellers claim to have knowledge about future events. However, the scripts are opposed in that politicians are supposed to be informed and knowledgeable, while fortune tellers are viewed as charlatans who make false claims. The joke plays on this contradiction by suggesting that politicians are no different from fortune tellers, as they also make predictions about the future without really knowing what will happen.

Figure A32: *Joke 1 SO Part 4/5.*

< 2/2 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. Politicians are knowledgeable and authoritative figures who can predict the future.
2. Politicians are ignorant and unreliable figures who actually know very little about what they claim to know.

These two scripts are opposed because they present two contradictory views of politicians: one as authoritative and knowledgeable and the other as unreliable and ignorant. The humor in the joke comes from the unexpected reversal of the audience's expectations, as the punchline reveals that the second script is actually true, while the first script is false.

Figure A33: *Joke 1 SO Part 5/5.*

 The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward and practical approach to solving a problem.
2. The script of reality TV shows, which involves sensationalism, drama, and often irrational behavior.

The joke plays on the contrast between these two scripts by suggesting that even a simple task like changing a lightbulb becomes an over-the-top, attention-seeking spectacle in the context of reality TV. The absurdity of the image of three people spinning around while trying to change a lightbulb highlights the clash between these two scripts.

Figure A34: *Joke 2 OR Part 1/5.*

< 2/2 > The two scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward and practical approach to a task.
2. The script of reality TV, which involves drama, excessive attention-seeking, and often superficial or meaningless actions.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that the first is associated with competence and utility, while the second is often seen as frivolous and shallow. The joke combines these two scripts by suggesting that even a simple task like changing a lightbulb can become an opportunity for reality TV stars to engage in attention-seeking behavior.

Figure A35: *Joke 2 OR Part 2/5.*

< 4/4 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, a joke is created by combining two different scripts that are compatible in some ways but are opposite in others. In the joke, "How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round," the two scripts that are being combined are:

1. The script for changing a light bulb, which involves a straightforward and practical approach to problem-solving. This script typically involves only one or two people, and they work together to solve the problem quickly and efficiently.
2. The script for a reality TV show, which involves drama, entertainment, and attention-seeking behavior. This script typically involves a large cast of characters who are more interested in being the center of attention than in solving practical problems.

These two scripts are compatible because they both involve multiple people working together to achieve a goal. However, they are also opposed because the reality TV script emphasizes drama and entertainment, while the light bulb script emphasizes practical problem-solving. The joke is funny because it combines these two scripts in an unexpected way, highlighting the absurdity of the situation and the contrast between the two scripts.

Figure A36: *Joke 2 OR Part 3/5.*

< 3/3 > The two scripts in this joke are:

1. The script for changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward and practical process of replacing a non-functioning bulb with a new one.
2. The script for reality TV, which involves drama, attention-seeking behavior, and often nonsensical or frivolous activities.

The joke plays on the contrast between these two scripts. While the task of changing a lightbulb is a simple and straightforward one, the involvement of reality TV stars turns it into a convoluted and absurd scenario, with three people needed to accomplish a basic task. The humor comes from the unexpected and ridiculous nature of the solution proposed, which is incompatible with the normal script for changing a lightbulb but perfectly in line with the script for reality TV.

Figure A37: *Joke 2 OR Part 4/5.*

< 5 / 5 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a simple and straightforward task that typically requires only one person.
2. The script of reality TV, which involves drama, spectacle, and attention-seeking behavior, often featuring multiple people competing for attention or status.

The joke plays on the clash between these two scripts by suggesting that the process of changing a lightbulb is transformed into a chaotic and dramatic scene involving three reality TV stars.

Figure A38: *Joke 2 OR Part 5/5.*

< 4 / 4 > The two scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward process of replacing a burnt-out bulb with a new one. This script is opposed by:
2. The script of reality TV, which involves drama, spectacle, and self-promotion rather than practical problem-solving. The humor in the joke arises from the contrast between the mundane task of changing a lightbulb and the exaggerated, attention-seeking behavior of reality TV stars.

Figure A39: *Joke 2 LA Part 1/5.*

 The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are the script for changing a light bulb and the script for reality TV stars.

The script for changing a light bulb involves a simple task that requires a limited number of people. It is a practical and mundane activity that is not usually associated with entertainment.

On the other hand, the script for reality TV stars is associated with drama, attention-seeking behavior, and the pursuit of fame. Reality TV stars are often depicted as shallow, vain, and self-absorbed.

By combining these two scripts, the joke plays on the contrast between the ordinary task of changing a light bulb and the exaggerated behavior of reality TV stars. The punchline suggests that the reality TV stars are so self-absorbed that they would need two people to spin one person holding a light bulb, rather than simply changing the bulb themselves.

Figure A40: *Joke 2 LA Part 2/5.*

Figure A41: *Joke 2 LA Part 3/5.*

Figure A42: *Joke 2 LA Part 4/5.*

Figure A43: *Joke 2 LA Part 5/5.*

Figure A44: *Joke 2 NS Part 1/5.*

 The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward, practical task that requires a certain level of competence and skill.
2. The script of reality TV, which is often associated with shallowness, attention-seeking behavior, and a lack of real-world skills or abilities.

These two scripts are opposed in that the first script requires a level of competency, while the second script is often associated with a lack of competency. However, the joke is compatible with both scripts because it combines them in an unexpected way, creating a humorous incongruity. The punchline of the joke subverts the expectation that more people would make the task easier, by instead making it more complicated and ridiculous.

Figure A45: *Joke 2 NS Part 2/5.*

< 2 / 2 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which is a common and straightforward task that people do at home or at work. This script involves the basic steps of removing the old bulb, replacing it with a new one, and testing the light. This script is compatible with the idea of efficiency and competence.
2. The script of reality TV stars, which refers to famous people who appear on reality shows for entertainment. This script involves the idea of superficiality, narcissism, and being famous for no apparent reason. This script is opposed to the idea of efficiency and competence, as reality TV stars are often criticized for lacking real talent or skills.

The joke plays on the contrast between these two scripts by suggesting that even two reality TV stars are not enough to change a lightbulb efficiently. The punchline implies that reality TV stars are useless in practical tasks and can only spin around aimlessly.

Figure A46: *Joke 2 NS Part 3/5.*

< 5 / 5 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a practical and straightforward approach to solving a problem. This script is opposed to:
2. The script of reality TV stars, which involves a focus on entertainment and often involves drama, exaggeration, and attention-seeking behavior.

The humor in this joke comes from the unexpected merging of these two scripts, as the punchline suggests that reality TV stars are not only ineffective at changing light bulbs, but they also become part of the problem and make it even more complicated.

Figure A47: *Joke 2 NS Part 4/5.*

< 4 / 4 > The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script for changing a lightbulb: This script involves a straightforward process of replacing a lightbulb that needs to be done with some basic skills and tools. It is a common task that most people can do without much difficulty.
2. The script for reality TV shows: This script involves people being put in contrived situations for the sake of entertainment, often with little regard for their actual skills or abilities. It is a form of entertainment that is often seen as shallow and lacking in substance.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that changing a lightbulb is a practical, necessary task, while reality TV shows are often seen as frivolous and unnecessary. By combining the two in the joke, the humor comes from the absurdity of imagining reality TV stars trying to perform a practical task and failing miserably. The punchline, where it takes three stars to change a lightbulb, adds another layer of absurdity by implying that they are so incompetent that they need to be spun around just to do a simple task.

Figure A48: *Joke 2 NS Part 5/5.*

< 4 / 4 > The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb - this script involves a straightforward process of replacing a burnt-out lightbulb with a new one.
2. The script of physical comedy - this script involves humorous situations that arise from physical actions and movements, such as spinning someone around.

These two scripts are opposed because the actions involved in changing a lightbulb are typically serious and practical, while physical comedy involves silly or absurd actions that are not typically associated with practical tasks. The joke works by combining these two scripts in a way that is unexpected and humorous.

Figure A49: *Joke 2 TA Part 1/5.*

 The two scripts that are compatible and opposed in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a simple and straightforward task of replacing a burnt-out lightbulb. It is a familiar and mundane task that people perform routinely.
2. The script of being foolish or stupid, which involves doing something in a silly, incompetent, or nonsensical manner. It is a common stereotype or caricature of people who lack intelligence or common sense.

The joke works by blending these two scripts in a way that creates a surprise or unexpected outcome. The punchline reveals that instead of changing the lightbulb in a normal or efficient way, the "idiots" in the joke perform a ridiculous and unnecessary action by spinning one person around while holding the bulb. This unexpected twist violates our expectations of the straightforward task of changing a lightbulb and makes us laugh at the absurdity of the situation.

Figure A50: *Joke 2 TA Part 2/5.*

< 5 / 5 > The Semantic Script Theory of Humor suggests that a joke involves two different scripts that are compatible in some way but are also opposed. In the given joke, the two scripts are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward and practical process of replacing a lightbulb that has burned out.
2. The script of physical comedy or slapstick humor, which involves characters engaging in ridiculous or absurd physical actions that are often accompanied by exaggerated movements or sound effects.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that the first script involves a practical task that requires focus and attention, while the second script involves physical antics that are often the result of carelessness or lack of attention. By combining these two scripts in the joke, the punchline creates a humorous and unexpected twist, as the idea of spinning someone around while changing a lightbulb is both absurd and impractical.

Figure A51: *Joke 2 TA Part 3/5.*

< 2 / 2 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke, according to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, are the scripts of "changing a lightbulb" and "being an idiot." These scripts are opposed because changing a lightbulb implies some level of competence and intelligence, while being an idiot implies the opposite. By combining these two scripts in the joke, the humor comes from the unexpected and illogical pairing of these two concepts.

Figure A52: *Joke 2 TA Part 4/5.*

< 3 / 3 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke, according to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, are:

1. The script for changing a lightbulb, which involves a straightforward and efficient process to replace the bulb.
2. The script for a foolish, ridiculous or incompetent behavior, in which the characters are depicted as being inept or incapable.

The joke plays on the idea that the second script is being inserted into the first script, resulting in an unexpected and humorous outcome. The punchline suggests that instead of a simple process of changing a lightbulb, the three individuals are engaging in a silly, pointless activity that is far from efficient or effective.

Figure A53: *Joke 2 TA Part 5/5.*

< 1/5 > In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Script 1: Reality TV stars being depicted as individuals who lack intelligence or skills.
This script is based on the common stereotype that reality TV stars are often portrayed as shallow or lacking talent in comparison to professionals in various fields.
2. Script 2: The process of drawing a picture requiring a specific division of labor.
This script highlights the conventional notion that drawing a picture typically involves one person holding the drawing utensil (pen) while another person moves the canvas or paper.

The joke juxtaposes the two scripts by humorously suggesting that reality TV stars are only capable of contributing to the drawing process by performing the menial task of holding the pen, while leaving the more essential task of moving the paper to two other individuals. The contrast between the expected and the absurd outcome is what creates the humor in this joke.

Figure A54: *Joke 2 SI Part 1/5.*

< 4/5 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, a joke is considered humorous when it combines two scripts that are compatible but opposed in some way. In the given joke, the two scripts that are being combined are:

1. Reality TV: This script refers to the popular genre of television shows that feature real people in unscripted situations. Reality TV often involves drama, competition, and exaggerated personalities.
2. Drawing a Picture: This script refers to the activity of creating a visual representation using a pen or pencil and paper. It implies a more serious and focused approach compared to the light-hearted nature of reality TV.

The joke relies on the clash between the two scripts. In the context of the joke, the expectation is that drawing a picture requires skill and concentration. However, the punchline subverts this expectation by suggesting that it only takes three reality TV stars to complete the task, with one holding the pen and two moving the paper. This implies that reality TV stars are not typically associated with artistic abilities or focus, thus contrasting the two scripts and creating humor.

Figure A55: *Joke 2 SI Part 2/5.*

< 2/5 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, jokes derive their humor from the collision or combination of two different scripts that are compatible but opposed in some way. In the given joke:

Script 1: The expectation of a reality TV star's lack of skills or incompetence in performing a task.

Script 2: The conventional understanding of how to draw a picture, which typically involves holding the paper steady while using the pen to create the drawing.

These two scripts are compatible because they both involve performing a task, but they are opposed because the reality TV stars are expected to be incapable or unskilled, contrasting with the conventional understanding of how to draw a picture. The joke plays on the humorous incongruity between these two opposing scripts, highlighting the irony of relying on reality TV stars to accomplish a task that requires basic drawing skills.

Figure A56: *Joke 2 SI Part 3/5.*

< 3 / 5 In the given joke, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Script of Reality TV: This script refers to the genre of reality television shows where individuals, often celebrities or aspiring stars, are depicted in various unscripted situations or challenges. The script typically involves drama, conflict, and attention-seeking behavior.
2. Script of Drawing or Art: This script refers to the activity of creating visual representations using pens, pencils, or other artistic tools. It involves skills such as holding the pen correctly and moving the paper to create the desired artwork.

The joke combines these two scripts in a humorous manner by subverting the expectation of a straightforward answer. Instead of providing a conventional response, the punchline suggests that it takes three reality TV stars to complete a simple task like drawing a picture, with one holding the pen and two others unnecessarily moving the paper. This playfully highlights the stereotypical notions of reality TV stars lacking practical skills or engaging in trivial tasks.

Figure A57: *Joke 2 SI Part 4/5.*

< 5 / 5 > In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. The script of "reality TV stars": This script refers to the individuals who appear on reality television shows, which are known for their focus on drama, sensationalism, and often being criticized for lacking substance or talent.
2. The script of "drawing a picture": This script refers to the act of creating an artwork by using a pen or pencil to make marks on a piece of paper. This script is associated with a more traditional and skill-based activity that requires precision and creativity.

The humor in this joke arises from the incongruity between these two scripts. Reality TV stars are typically not associated with artistic skills or the ability to draw well. By combining the two scripts, the joke suggests that even with their limited skills, it takes three reality TV stars to accomplish a task that might typically be done by a single person in the "drawing a picture" script.

Figure A58: *Joke 2 SI Part 5/5.*

 The two scripts in the joke are:

1. The expectation that reality TV stars are not intelligent or competent enough to perform simple tasks like changing a lightbulb.
2. The common situation of multiple people being involved in a simple task, resulting in confusion and inefficiency.

These two scripts are opposed in the sense that the first script implies a lack of ability or competence, while the second script suggests that multiple people working together should be more efficient. The joke plays on this contrast by using the expectation of incompetence associated with reality TV stars to subvert the expected outcome of the situation.

Figure A59: *Joke 2 LM Part 1/5.*

Figure A60: *Joke 2 LM Part 2/5.*

Figure A61: *Joke 2 LM Part 3/5.*

Figure A62: *Joke 2 LM Part 4/5.*

Figure A63: *Joke 2 LM Part 5/5.*

The Semantic Script Theory of Humor suggests that the joke is compatible with two different scripts that are opposed in some way. In this joke, the two scripts are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb: This script is a familiar scenario where someone needs to change a lightbulb that is not working.
2. The script of reality TV stars: This script involves the stereotypical behavior of reality TV stars, which is often characterized by drama, conflicts, and over-the-top reactions.

The two scripts are opposed in that changing a lightbulb is a mundane, straightforward task, while the behavior of reality TV stars is often seen as exaggerated and dramatic. The humor in the joke arises from the unexpected combination of these two scripts and the twist at the end that plays on the viewer's expectations about reality TV stars.

Figure A64: *Joke 2 SO Part 1/5.*

< 2 / 2 >

According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, this joke involves two scripts that are opposed in some way but still compatible. The first script is a typical scenario where someone changes a lightbulb, and the second script involves a common trope in reality TV where contestants argue and fight with each other.

In this joke, the two scripts are blended together, and the reality TV script is used to create a surprising and humorous twist on the mundane task of changing a lightbulb. The joke suggests that reality TV stars are so prone to arguing and fighting that even a simple task like changing a lightbulb becomes an opportunity for drama and conflict.

Figure A65: *Joke 2 SO Part 2/5.*

< 3 / 3 >

The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb: This script involves a simple and straightforward task of changing a lightbulb. It is an ordinary, mundane task that does not require any drama or fuss.
2. The script of reality TV shows: This script involves highly dramatic and exaggerated scenarios, often involving fights, arguments, and conflicts among the participants.

The joke relies on the contrast between these two scripts. The first part of the joke sets up the expectation that changing a lightbulb is a simple task that can be accomplished by one person. The punchline subverts this expectation by introducing the reality TV script and suggesting that even a simple task like changing a lightbulb can turn into a dramatic and chaotic event when reality TV stars are involved.

Figure A66: *Joke 2 SO Part 3/5.*

< 4/4 > The two scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb: This script involves a simple task of changing a lightbulb and typically doesn't involve any conflict or drama.
2. The script of reality TV shows: This script involves participants engaging in conflicts, arguments, and drama for the entertainment of viewers. Reality TV shows are often criticized for being overly dramatic and lacking in substance.

These two scripts are opposed because the script of changing a lightbulb is mundane and straightforward, while the script of reality TV shows is dramatic and conflict-ridden. The joke plays on the contrast between these two scripts by using the setting of a simple task, changing a lightbulb, and applying the characteristics of a reality TV show to it, resulting in a humorous outcome.

Figure A67: *Joke 2 SO Part 4/5.*

< 5/5 > The two compatible, opposed scripts in this joke are:

1. The script of changing a lightbulb: This script involves a person or people changing a lightbulb that is no longer functioning. This script is compatible with the joke because the first part of the joke sets up the question, "How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb?"
2. The script of reality TV drama: This script involves people on a reality TV show having dramatic conflicts with one another. This script is compatible with the joke because the punchline suggests that the reality TV stars would argue about who is responsible for breaking the old lightbulb instead of simply changing it.

The two scripts are opposed because the first script is straightforward and mundane, while the second script is typically exaggerated and over-the-top. The contrast between the two scripts creates the surprise and amusement that is the essence of the joke.

Figure A68: *Joke 2 SO Part 5/5.*